

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Experimental monitoring system management report

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Partners involved in the work execution

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NOTES:

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For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

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Executive summary

This report describes the management plan of the experimental systems deployed in the Deduru Oya basin area of Sri Lanka.

1 Introduction

Under the 4onse research project, 32 weather stations have been installed in Sri Lanka. Out of them, 27 have been installed in Deduru Oya basin and 02 stations have been installed outside the basin, at Lankapura and Walapane Divisional Secretariat Divisions. The remaining three (03) stations have been installed in University of Moratuwa for testing purposes. Figure 1 shows the locations of the 4ONSE weather stations and the river gauges deployed in Deduru Oya basin. Maintenance work has been done by two full time-based staff members. Stations in the Deduru Oya basin are visited every week (14 stations per week). Each station is visited per two weeks. In addition, two officers from respective Divisional Secretariat Office have been appointed to carry out the maintenance activities of the stations installed at Lankapura and Walapane locations. The management plan of the stations has been elaborated in section 2.

Figure 1- Locations of the 4ONSE weather stations and river gauges deployed in Deduru Oya basin

2 Management plan of the 4ONSE stations

2.1 Stations assigned for each staff member

The field visits were arranged two days per week. The 27 weather stations have been divided among two staff members. One member covers approximately 6-7 stations during each visit. Accordingly, a total of 13-14 stations cover by two members within one week. Table 1 shows the stations assigned for each staff member.

	Staff member 1	Staff member 2
1	Kokkawila Kanishta Vidyalaya (KKW)	Lyceum internantional school (LIS)
2	Wellangiriya Farm (WLG)	Paragahedeniya National School (PGD)
3	Hettipola Mahindodaya Maha Vidyalaya (HTP)	Wewala Parakrama Kanishta Vidyalaya (WWL)
4	Bamunugama Maha Vidyalaya (BMG)	Rambadagalla Central College (RBG)
5	Withikuliya Central College (WTK)	Kadapathwehera Vidyalaya (KDW)
6	Sri Sudarshanaramaya (SSR)	Bathalagoda Rice Research Institute (RRI)
7	Hulogedara Maha Vidyalaya (HGR)	Malagane Maha Vidyalaya (MLG)
8	Bakmeegahawaththa School (BMG)	S B Herath National School (SBH)
9	Gunapala Malalasekara Model School (GMM)	Sir John Kothalawela Central College (SJK)
10	Gajaneggama Maha Vidyalaya (GJM)	Medamulla De Mel Maha Vidyalaya (MDM)
11	Daduru Oya Dam (DAM)	Kumbukgate Central College (KBG)
12	Polpithigama Central College (PPG)	Porapola Kanishta Vidyalaya (PPL)
13	Hakwatuna Reservoir (HKW)	Kimbulwana Oya (KMB)
14	Maeliya School (MEL)	

2.2 What to bring on a field visit

The following items are necessary to carry for a field visit

Required Tools & equipment

- 10mm, 13mm, 17mm wrinches
- Rain gauge caibration equipments
- Cable ties
- Insulation tapes & silicone.
- Philips screwdrivers & flat screwdrivers
- Nuts and washers.
- Ladder and long brush
- Wire stripper & cutter
- Grease

Required replacement parts (if necessary)

- BME sensors
- Temperature sensors
- BME shields
- Data loggers & SD cards
- Sim 800C module.
- Wind speed & wind direction sensors
- Solar charger & panels
- Solar charger & reset circuits
- Extra MOD board
- Extra PCB board
- RTC modules & CMOS batteries
- Wires & etc.
- Batteries

2.3 Steps to follow before going for the maintenance.

- Scrutinize the previous data of the stations and identify the faulty sensors.
- Arrange the tools & required replacement parts.
- Plan the route to use the available time to the maximum.
- Identify the not working stations which are exclude from the weekly route & adjust the route plan accordingly.

2.4 Maintenance procedure

1. Open the system boxes and power down the system.
2. Scrutinize internal & external wiring assembly and electronic components. Replace them if needed.
3. Check battery voltage and power levels of the solar panel output.
4. Check voltage for the system.
5. Check the solar charger or solar charger & reset circuit thoroughly. Replace or repair if needed.

6. Clean the battery terminals and grease them.
7. Do the repairs as needed.
8. Look for any defects on the enclosures, circuitry, poles and etc.
9. Clean the BME shield, BME sensor and temperature sensor.
10. Clean the rain gauge, wind speed and wind direction sensors.
11. Grease the components as required.
12. Check the wiring again and power the station.
13. Monitor if all the things are happening accordingly.
14. Complete the maintenance report on the "ODK Collect" maintenance application.

2.5 "ODK Collect" maintenance application

This application was developed by team members of SUPSI to report the maintenance activities. The application works online or offline. The form can be sent to the server whenever you have a stable Internet connection. Figure 2 shows some screenshots of the maintenance app. The steps for setting-up the application is given below:

- Use an Android phone to install the app "ODK Collect" (google play store);
- Open the app
- Click on the 3 points on the up-right corner
- Click on "general settings"
- Click on "server"
- Insert the following address under the URL label: <https://geoservice.ist.supsi.ch/odk/>
- Go back and click on the "User and device identity"
- Click on "form metadata"
- Insert the information in the "user-defined" section
- Go to the homescreen of the app
- Click on "Get Blank Form"
- Check the form "4onse - Maintenance check-list (v0.1)"
- Click on "Get selected" button on the bottom-right
- Go back and start the maintenance clicking on the "Fill blank form" and compiling the form

Figure 2 - Some screenshots of the ODK Collect maintenance application

2.6 Steps to follow after the maintenance visits

- Monitor the repaired station if they are working accordingly.
- Send the maintenance reports through the “ODK Collect” maintenance app.
- Log the work carried out and any special observations & etc.

3 Conclusion

This report includes the management plan of the 4ONSE stations deployed in Deduru Oya basin. Two staff members were assigned to carryout this task, by dividing the 27 weather stations among themselves. The report includes the required backpack components for the field visit and the procedure of carrying out the maintenance activities. Further, it also elaborates the things to follow before and after the field visits. A special application called "ODK Collect" which was developed by the team members of SUPSI was used to report the maintenance activities of the stations.